

microbiology staff. The participants visited outlying fertilizer experiments and rice-growing areas in the Philippines.

Candidates for INSFFER training are carefully selected. Only highly motivated

and active soil scientists with a B.S. degree or its equivalent, leadership potential, and a knack for hard work can quality.

The training program was developed

by a committee composed of Dr. E.T. Craswell, Dr. J. T. Cope. and Dr. L. E. Nelson, chairman. Mr. Rogelio Rosales was training assistant in charge of the program. ■

Algae multiplication and fertilizer practices

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Blue-green algae were inoculated in bulk fields of the Aduthurai Paddy Experiment Station in 1976 and 1977. Spread of the algae to all of the farm's wetland fields, including experimental areas, necessitated algae control, particularly in manurial experiments.

Blue-green algae were found embedded in plots of the 40th crop of the permanent manurial experiments 7 days after transplanting in 1978 kharif. Because the treatments included applications of both organic and inorganic forms of nitrogen, as well as many combinations of phosphorus, potassium, and lime (L), separate estimates of the algae's spread in various plots were made to determine the conditions of relative

Mean algae yield at Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Main plots	Algae yield (kg/28 m ² plot)								Mean
	0	P	K	L	PK	PL	KL	PKL	
Control	0.8	5.4	2.4	0.8	6.0	3.3	2.0	4.1	3.1
Ammonium sulfate	0.7	3.0	0.5	0.3	3.0	0.5	0.4	2.2	1.4
Compost	2.2	5.9	7.4	0.9	4.8	3.8	1.5	4.3	3.2
Farmyard manure	1.9	4.5	1.7	1.2	4.0	2.8	1.9	3.7	2.7
Green leaf	1.2	5.5	1.3	0.8	5.5	4.2	1.1	3.9	2.9
Mean	1.4	4.8	1.6	0.8	4.6	3.0	1.4	3.6	

^aP = phosphorus, K = potassium, L = lime. C.D. for main treatment, 0.72 kg; C.D. for subtreatment, 1.34 kg; interaction, N.S.

adaptation.

Algae were harvested from each plot 15 days after planting, and yields were analyzed.

Among the main treatments, the plot that received ammonium sulfate gave the lowest yields (see table). In 1978, Venkataraman observed that nitrogen application immobilizes P in the soil. Possibly, algae grew poorly because only a negligible quantity of P was available in the plots fertilized with ammonium

sulfate. The absence of readily available nitrogen in the other treatments caused higher P availability to the algae and consequently, significantly higher algae yields.

The algae yields from P, PK, PKL, and PL were superior to those from O, K, KL, and L. That suggests that on this soil K and L influence algae yield only when phosphorus is applied. Thus, for successful multiplication the phosphorus requirements of the algae must be met. ■

Environment and its influence

Rice fertilizer made of hydrolysis lignin

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Industries in the USSR produce 800,000 t of hydrolysis lignin/year. Of that, 520,000 t are not used and are wasted, polluting the environment. The All-union Research Institute of Hydrolysis in Leningrad produces fertilizer from it. The lignin-stimulating fertilizer (LSF) (which can be made of rice husks) is the product of the Andijan Hydrolysis Plant

Changes in nucleic acid metabolism in rice apexes due to the effects of lignin-stimulating fertilizer (LSF). Kuan Agricultural Institute, Krasnodar, USSR, 1974-78.

Leaf no.	RNA-DNA ratio in apexes			
	Without LSF	0.5 t LSF/ha	2.5 t LSF/ha	12.5 t LSF/ha
Leaf without blade	3.2	4.6	4.1	3.5
1	2.1	4.3	4.2	3.9
3	2.1	4.5	4.5	4.4
4	2.0	5.0	4.8	4.5
5	1.3	5.6	5.0	4.3
7	2.8	5.9	4.8	3.8
9	3.4	5.7	4.5	3.4
11	3.5	5.1	4.2	3.2

(Data after statistical analysis)

in the Uzbek SSR. It consists of nine parts hydrolysis lignin and one part ammoniac salts of polycarbonic acids. These salts, the active part of LSF, can be recovered after the lignin is hydrolyzed with nitric acid (HNO₃) and the product

is reduced with ammonia (NH₃).

In laboratory experiments from 1974 through 1978, rice yields increased by 10% (from 5.5 to 6.1 t/ha) when 0.4 t LSF/ha was applied before sowing. The increase resulted from the active

tillering brought about by the changes in nucleic acid metabolism in rice apexes

(see table). The LSF decreases the activity of endogenous rice gibberellins

and the silica (SiO₂) content of the straw. The latter can cause rice lodging.

Constraints to high yields

Farmers' perceptions of constraints to high yields in wetland paddy

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A study was conducted to determine farmers' perceptions of the relative contribution of socioeconomic and biologic constraints to high yields in kharif or wetland paddy. Among the biophysical constraints considered were water management, situation-specific rice varieties, weed control, insect and disease incidence, problem soils, soil fertility, and cultural management. Socioeconomic constraints were knowledge, institutional credit, absentee land-ownership, the sharecropping system, village leadership, input availability, marketing of farm produce, adequate legislation, fragmentation of holding, farming tradition, and risk aversion.

Stratified random samples were taken in 14 villages. The farmers were thoroughly briefed on the significance of the constraints and asked to rate their perceptions of each. A total of 189 marginal, small, and large farmers tilled in score sheets, which were tabulated. Score values on individual constraints were obtained by multiplying the rank marked by the farmers by the frequency. The ranking of each constraint was obtained in terms of percentage from the total rank score given by the farmers against the biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. The data are presented in the table; yield constraints (%) in kharif rice are in the figure. ■

Farmers' ranking of biophysical and socioeconomic constraints. West Bengal, India.

Constraint	All farmers' rank (n = 189)	Rank given by		
		Marginal farmers ^a (n = 139)	Small farmers ^b (n = 38)	Large farmers ^c (n = 12)
Biophysical				
Insect pests and diseases	1	1	2	2
Water management	2	2	1	1
Soil and fertility	3	3	4	3
Situation-specific rice varieties	4	4	3	4
Cultural management	5	5	5	5
Weed control	6	6	6	6
Socioeconomic				
Institutional credit	1	1	2	1
Input availability	2	2	1	2
Knowledge	3	3	4	3
Village leadership	4	4	5	4
Marketing of farm produce	5	5	3	5
Legislation safeguarding farmers' interest	6	7	6	6
Tradition	7	6	7	7
Fragmentation of landholding	8	8	8	8
Risk aversion	9	10	9	9
Absentee landowner	10	9	10	10

^a Holding as much as 1 ha of land. ^b Holding from 1 to 2 ha ^c Holding more than 2 ha.

Proportion (%) of farmers mentioning biophysical and socioeconomic constraints on kharif rice, West Bengal, India.